

The Biblical Hermeneutics: Literary Genre

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Abstract: A literary genre is a grouping of similar literary works based on their content and structure, such as tone, attitude or subject (McLean, 2012). The Bible is a work of literature, written in a mix of different literary genres, each of which requires special attention. Since the Bible has been written many years ago, these genres would have been more familiar to old readers than they are to the contemporary reader. However, genre differences necessitate specific rules for the interpretation of any literary work, where one of the general principles is that the author's words should be interpreted according to the literary genre in which they occur (Schwartz, 1971). The way one approaches a poem is not the same way s/he approaches a historical narrative. A solid interpretation is therefore governed to some extent by genre. In this piece of writing, the theoretical bases of different literary genres will be explained, illustrating their use in biblical scriptures to achieve the author's goals.

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Biblical Narratives

The Bible is full of narratives, consisting of stories predominant, for example, in the Pentateuch, the historical books in the Old Testament as well as in the Gospels and Acts in the New Testament. The content of Biblical narratives is true history that creates an environment to convey factual events about God's presence in human history (Hamilton, 1998). They are neither allegorical nor figurative nor mythical phenomena.

Although this is the true history, some Christians may have the wrong tendency to teach it as if it is ahistorical (Fredericksen, et al., 2021). It would therefore be wrong to read it as a series of morality stories or like an inspirational fiction. It is important to stick to the theological nature of Biblical narratives because the hope of salvation of the Christians rests on their truthfulness. For example, one learns that Jesus was a real man who fulfilled the promises of the Old Testament. He truly died and rose from the dead, which is why such facts must be remembered. Narratives are therefore real facts about history. However, readers should recognize that the authors do not just put the facts in order, but write history to make a theological point.

While narratives are selective with authors giving only what is enough to make their point, narratives consist of ancient history, hence the use of conventions of ancient writing. For example, there is use of loose quotations and round numbers but no use of footnotes. This makes it impossible to hold ancient writers to modern conventions of writing.

An example of biblical narrative is found in Matthew 1, where the genealogy of Jesus was presented. The first sixteen verses are genealogy and readers do not often read it all, yet this is a pure genealogy. Why does the reader want to skip this? Perhaps, he does not see a theological point that Matthew is making. However, Matthew shows that Jesus is the long-awaited king in the

line of David, the Messiah, and that he is the one in the line of Abraham who would bring blessing to all the earth (Gen. 22:18). To do so, Matthew uses a narrative history to make this point. This is confirmed by John 20:30-31, which reads as follow:

Jesus performed many other signs in the presence of his disciples, which are not recorded in this book. ³¹ But these are written that you may believe that Jesus is the Messiah, the Son of God, and that by believing you may have life in his name.

What theological point is John making in these gospel scriptures? These verses are preceded by the accounts of the miracles Jesus performed, many of which have not been recorded as John points out. John wrote these with a purpose to convince the readers that Jesus is the Christ, the Son of God. This is how biblical narratives work, they are used with a theological point, as Klaasen (2017) stresses.

Therefore, if one approaches a narrative portion of the Bible, s/he should solely research the theology of the text, to understand the point that the author is making.

Poetry

Poetry is found particularly in the Old Testament as in the Psalms and Song of Solomon. Even a few narrative books contain occasional songs or poems. This type of literary genre is a concentrated language because it squeezes a maximum of thought into a minimum of words. As Berlin (2020) explains, a most common characteristic of poetry is parallelism, where the authors pair up two parallel elements. Meek (1929) is so clear that, unlike English poetry, Hebrew poetry does not use rhyme but parallelism.

Psalm 2 is a good example, where the psalmist uses synonymous parallelism to do a lot of things. In this type of parallelism, the second line repeats the thought of the first line in different words. For example if one takes Psalm 2:10 “Therefore, you kings, be wise; be warned, you rulers of the earth”, it is clear that the psalmist gives a parallel order where he says the same thing twice, hence a poetic weight but the same meaning. One also observes synonymous parallelism in verse 1, 3, 5 and 9. Verses 8 and 2 also have incomplete and parallelism in the first half respectively.

According to Meek (1929), one can also observe antithetical parallelism, where the second part presents the same idea as the first by contrast or negation. This type of parallelism is found, for example, in Psalm 1:6 which reads: “*For the Lord watches over the way of the righteous, but the way of the wicked leads to destruction*”.

Another broader category of parallelism that Berlin (1992) distinguishes in the Hebrew Scriptures is synthetic parallelism which involves the completion or expansion of the idea of part one into part two. This is evident, for example, in Psalm 42:1 “As the deer pants for streams of water, so my soul pants for you, my God”.

In all, poetry consists of a non-metric form of verse characterized primarily by verbal inventiveness, noticeable poetic diction and texture, and conciseness. This particular literary form consists of short lines, often of two words, whose dense form of is obtained by bringing together semantically important words. It involves higher concentrations of words and phrases with rare meanings or uses, bold ellipses, sudden transitions, and other stylistic complexities. It is necessary to read poetry as part of the larger discipline of literary studies. If someone is studying or teaching

from biblical poetry, he should pay attention to the structure of the poem. Look at the parallelism. Ask how it is used.

Biblical wisdom

Wisdom literature is more apparent in the wisdom books of the Bible such as in Job, Proverbs, and Ecclesiastes. These are extremely practical books intended to help Christians live well in the world. Wisdom literature appears in lots of forms such as parables, stories and confessions.

One of the major considerations in the wisdom literature, according to Goldsworthy (2011), is context. For example, one can be misled to see that a lot of what Jobs says is wrong if one is not paying attention to the context. Likewise, parts of Ecclesiastes are difficult to understand unless context is added.

Since wisdom literature is about teaching and is context-focused, one must read the whole book in light of these Closing comments. If one needs to study or teach wisdom literature to others, one should focus is on application.

Biblical Prophecy

Several of the books of the Old Testament were written by prophets, the spokespersons of God who received a message from God through dreams or visions and then communicated it to His people (Keathley, 2006).

According to Rowley (1945), prophetic messages had either foretelling or forthtelling aspects or both together. Perhaps most people would view prophets as people who predict the future; although foretelling is one aspect of prophetic work and it is not always the main point of

the prophetic books. The main content is forthtelling, meaning that the prophets spoke of the truth of God to the people of their day, telling people to repent and directing them back to the covenant with God. Thus, if one approaches the prophetic books as a series of predictions about the future, the author's intention is missing. Prophetic Scriptures are not mere blueprints for all of human history. They have both the predictive aspect, for example when Isaiah announces the sufferings of Christ, and the revelatory aspect in which the prophets speak of God's anger towards sin and His will to be merciful. When studying these texts, one should allow the text to speak for itself.

Biblical Apocalyptic

This kind of literature may seem exotic to the modern person. It derives its name from a Greek word whose meaning is to reveal (Swartz, 2009). Apocalyptic literature is evident in Revelation, Daniel, Matthew, 2 Thessalonians and some others. This form of literature consists in shrinking the veil which reveals to the reader the great spiritual conflict which is generally invisible, letting readers understand the true meaning and destination of history. It is characterized by the appearance of a heavenly messenger (an Angel), a vision, strange symbolism and numbers, an expectation of future salvation, and a message of judgment on the present age.

Apocalyptic scriptures are perhaps the most difficulty to understand or the most abused of the literary genres. Most of the foolish arguments come from a misunderstanding of the apocalyptic scriptures and this is not surprising because they are the most difficult biblical texts to understand (Petersen, 2017).

When approaching apocalyptic scriptures, it is advisable to read the text with humility. Once one acknowledges his limitations, he should work hard to try to understand what these texts are saying. Christians should always be willing to change their understanding of the word of God,

if they learn something better, because the scriptures are true and unchanging. No need to feel bad if one does not have perfect knowledge.

Another important advice for apocalyptic readers is to read these texts theologically. The focus of apocalyptic messages is to show that God is in control even when things are at their worst. He will eventually gain victory. Although it is good to understand what the number 666 means, spoken in Revelation 13; the main point is to get Christians to trust God and to persevere in the faith even when it is difficult, because they know that He will put things in order in the end.

However, it is equally important to approach the apocalyptic scriptures with good resources. Comparing a few different books on the subject would be a useful tip to undertake, especially if one is studying the apocalyptic.

Epistles

Epistle is a sophisticated word for letter, the predominant form of New Testament literature (Burton, 1905), which is arguably the simplest books in the Bible. This literature involves personal communication between one party and another in the form of address, salutation, body, and blessing.

Because the majority of epistles are context specific, it is important to identify their audience and the author's occasion. For example, some epistles appear to have been written to churches or to individuals, facing specific problems. One will therefore better understand the letter if he takes some time to try to understand the historical context of the letter. It would also be inappropriate to separate the various motives that an author may have in writing. However, when it becomes difficult to identify central occasion or purpose, one may interpret epistle in accordance with all of the concerns presented in the epistle itself.

Epistles are logical in nature, which is why readers should work to understand their logical development. Because the Epistles often seek to present strong arguments, readers should not only rip out individual chapters or verses, but also seek to understand the entire flow of argument in a book.

Overall, the Bible is a literary work that presents a variety of literary genres. Each genre has unique characteristics that govern the process of interpretation. The principles involved in understanding a parable are not the same for a historical narrative. Regardless of the genre, the content itself testifies to God's purposes and there is no contradiction in the sense. The difference comes from the need to communicate complementary ideas. The common thread is the communicated subject.

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